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LEARNING DISABILITIES: ETIOLOGY AND TYPES

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Abstract

This paper deals with the Etiology and Types of Learning disabilities. Learning disabilities are actually a failure on the part of the child who lacks adequate intelligence, maturation level, cultural background and educational experience to learn a scholastic skill. Such disabilities can only be determined by a psychologist, a paediatrician, or a psychiatrist. People with these disorders can find difficulty to learn as quickly as others who are not affected by the problem. The presentation discusses the five models, which act as etiological factors in learning difficulty. All these models are interlinked; hence, learning disability is multifactorial. Learning disabilities are of two types: based on information processing- input, integration, storage, and output; by function impaired- dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia etc.

Key words: Etiology of Learning disabilities, Dyslexia, Dysgraphia, Dyscalculia.

Introduction

The school system in India is expanding to provide education to all children in India. The fact that the government is trying to reach out to all sections of society is commendable. However, this also throws up a large number of students who are unable to cope with the educational system due to various factors. The educational machinery has not been geared sufficiently to deal with the intricacies that are an obvious outcome of garnering to large number of students. Among these factors, learning difficulties or learning disorders as they are variously used has a prominent place. The term learning disability can be used either in a broad sense or in a narrow sense. In a broad sense the term has different connotations and can be associated with any type of factor including mental retardation, brain injury, sensory difficulties or emotional disturbance. This would be a chromosomal defect in case of retardation or accident related brain injuries. The usage of learning disability is generally used more in a narrow sense. In a narrow sense it refers to the failure on the part of the child who has adequate intelligence, maturational level, cultural background and educational experience, to learn a scholastic skill. The narrower meaning is more explicitly designated in by the term 'specific learning disability.' It is a classification that includes several areas of functioning in which a person has difficulty learning in a typical manner, usually caused by an unknown factor. The

unknown factor is the brain's ability to receive and process information. In the narrower sense there could be deficits in reading, arithmetic or writing skills.

The terms learning disability and learning disorder are often used interchangeably though they differ in many ways. The term 'disorder' refers to significant learning problems in an academic area, which may not be sufficient to warrant an official definition. This may be a more informal classification that can be viewed as a general usage term for explaining a student's weakness in certain academic areas. The term learning disability is on the other hand an official clinical diagnosis that may be used for various legal and official purposes. It is determined by a psychologist, paediatrician or psychiatrist. The difference in usage is in the degree, frequency and intensity of the reported symptoms. When the term learning disorder is used it describes characteristics which include the inadequate development of specific academic, language, and speech skills. People with these disorders can find difficulty to learn as quickly as others who are not affected by the problem and they may have trouble performing specific types of skills or completing tasks if taught in conventional ways. The challenges they face are often pervasive through their life span. They may require special teaching methods to remediate their deficits and reach optimal level of performance.

There are ongoing controversies regarding learning disabilities. DSM IV does not use the term learning disability. In DSM V learning disorders are not limited to a particular diagnosis such as reading, mathematics and written expression. The DSM V uses a single diagnosis criteria describing drawbacks in the general academic skills and includes detailed specifics for the areas of reading, mathematics and written expression.

Etiology of learning disability

The etiological factors in learning disability are explained by five models.

- a. The difference model: This model states that individual differences in cognitive ability tend to be normally distributed throughout a given population and learning difficulties result from the natural occurrence of poorly developed cognitive skills.
- b. The deficit model: This model postulates learning difficulties that are associated with organic conditions that interfere with learning. These may include mixed cerebral dominance, maldevelopment or disease of the brain, vestibular difficulties and ocular difficulties.
- c. The delay model: In this model, learning difficulties are associated with immaturity in development which eventually will be resolved and academic skills will develop.
- d. The disruption model: This postulates that, extraneous factors such as anxiety or depression are disrupting the learning process.
- e. The personal-historical model: This model suggests that the student has not acquired the basic skills needed for learning because of environmental factors such as failure in the teaching or learning process.

These models offer various explanations for learning disability and no single model could explain the disabilities completely. The models are not mutually exclusive and elements of each cause may be associated with other causes. This would be indicative that learning disability is multifactorial.

Types of learning disabilities

The classification of the disorder is based on by either the type of information processing affected by the disability or by the specific difficulties caused by a processing deficit (a) Based on information processing. (b) By function impairment

- a. Based on information processing: The disability could be in any of the four stages of information processing used in learning: input, integration, storage and output.

- i. **Input**
Difficulties with visual perception can cause problems with recognizing the shape, position, or size of items seen. There could be problems with temporal perception. Auditory processing difficulties could make it difficult to screen out competing sounds.
 - ii. **Integration**
This has to deal with the process of categorizing, placing in sequence or placing into previous learning. Students with problems may not be able to memorize sequence of information. They may not be able to put facts together to see the 'big picture.' A poor vocabulary may result in problems with comprehension.
 - iii. **Storage**
The student may not have short-term memory or working memory, or long term memory. This may make it difficult to learn new material without more repetitions than usual. Difficulties with visual memory make the child it difficult to learn spellings.
 - iv. **Output**
The brain outputs information through words or muscle activity. Difficulties with language output could create problems with spoken language. These could result in responding on demand. In which one must retrieve information from storage, organize our thoughts, and put thoughts into words before we speak. A similar problem could occur when using the written language. Problems with motor activity (gross or fine motor), may cause stumbling, falling, bumping, bad handwriting, difficulty in tying shoelaces and the like.
- b. **By function impaired:** The deficit in any area of information processing can manifest in a variety of specific learning difficulties. This may be comorbid with other learning difficulties. There could be a reading disability, written expression disability or math disability.
- i. **Dyslexia:** Reading disorder is common with nearly a 70-80% of all students with specific learning disabilities having this condition. Dyslexia is only one among this type. A reading disability can affect any part of the reading process, including difficulty with accurate or fluent word recognition, or both, word decoding, reading rate, prosody (oral reading with expression), and reading comprehension. Indicators of this difficulty could include difficulty with phonemic awareness-the ability to break up words into their component sounds, and difficulty with matching letter combinations to specific sounds.
 - ii. **Dysgraphia:** is the writing disorder. Writing skills are substantially below those expected, based on the chronological age, measured intelligence and age appropriate education. Tasks requiring composition of written text may also be in deficit. There will be problems in grammatical and punctuation errors and poor paragraph organization, multiple spelling errors and penmanship.
 - iii. **Dyscalculia:** Such people are said to have poor math sense. It involves difficulties in learning maths concepts, memorizing math facts, organizing numbers and their organization.

Conclusion

An understanding of the etiology and types of learning disabilities is only the first step in creating an equitable atmosphere of education for all in our country. The next step would involve the use of remediation measures. This paper has only tried to deal with the limited perspective of etiology and types and it is hoped that this will provide an impetus for a deeper understanding of a need for identifying and correcting lacuna in the educational system.

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